

Interaction of Cognitive Linguistics with Other Disciplines: Cognitive Psychology

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Abstract. *This article details the main issues of cognitive linguistics and cognitive psychology, the interrelationships of these disciplines and their relationship with other disciplines. The relationships of cognitive linguistics with language and thinking, language and memory, language and perception relations, as well as neuropsychology, linguistics, artificial intelligence and psycholinguistics are analyzed. The article explores how cognitive processes work and the effects of these processes on understanding and using human language.*

Key words: *cognitive linguistics, Cognitive Psychology, Language and thinking, perception, neuropsychology, linguistics.*

Introduction

Cognitive linguistics is a science that studies the human language, the processes of its understanding and use. This science studies how language is related to cognitive processes, what knowledge is acquired and processed through language. Cognitive psychology, on the other hand, studies human processes of learning, memory, thinking, and decision making. This article details the main issues of cognitive linguistics and cognitive psychology and their relationship with other disciplines.

Cognitive linguistics is an actively developing field of modern, scientific research. Cognitive linguistics is recognized as one of the central areas of cognitology, the science of human cognition. The term cognitive is derived from the English word "cognitive – related to cognition", which goes back to Latin and Greek, is related to the concepts of cognition, perception, thinking. Knowledge of the world, reality, perception, reflection in consciousness and language, access to communication through language, transmission and reception of information is not a simple phenomenon. Cognitive linguistics is not limited to the theory of cognition in philosophy, but connects language with thinking and deeply scientific studies of the inextricable relationship of psychological, biological and neurophysiological aspects in its formation with social, cultural, linguistic phenomena.

Main part

Cognitive linguistics studies several important issues, including:

- Language and thinking relations: interactions between language and thinking, logical and semantic structures of language.
- Language learning and development: how the processes of learning and developing the language, how children and adults acquire the language.
- Language and memory: the relationship between language and memory, the processes of storage and processing of memories through language.

- Language comprehension and use: processes of language comprehension, analysis and use, cognitive mechanisms of language.

Cognitive psychology studies human cognitive processes, including:

- Perception and attention: how human cognition and attention work, how they are managed and analyzed.
- Memory: different types of memory (daytime, long-term and short-term memory) and the relationship between them.
- Education and learning: educational processes, methods of education and the effectiveness of Education.
- Problem solving and decision making: ways to solve problems, decision-making processes and their cognitive foundations.

Cognitive linguistics and Cognitive Psychology

Cognitive linguistics and cognitive psychology are in many ways closely related disciplines that explore different aspects of human consciousness. Below we will consider their main links:

Language and memory

The relationship between language and memory shows the interrelationships of cognitive linguistics and cognitive psychology. Humans keep new words and phrases in their memories and use them whenever necessary. What role the different types of memory play in the process of learning and understanding the language is the object of study of these disciplines.

Language Acquisition

Issues of how children and adults learn and develop language are also one of the main areas of research in cognitive linguistics and cognitive psychology. How children acquire language quickly and efficiently, and what cognitive processes are involved in language acquisition also show the interrelationships of these disciplines.

Language and perception

The relationship between language and perception is also a research topic of cognitive linguistics and cognitive psychology. How humans perceive, analyze, and process information they receive through language shows the complexity of cognitive processes.

Relationship Of Cognitive Linguistics With Other Disciplines

Cognitive linguistics has Interactions Not only with cognitive psychology, but also with many other disciplines:

Neuropsychology studies the relationship of cognitive processes to brain activity. Cognitive linguistics, in collaboration with neuropsychology, studies how language relates to brain function. Research in this area reveals the relationship between language and different parts of the brain.

Traditional linguistics is a central part of cognitive linguistics. Areas of linguistics such as phonetics, syntax, semantics serve as the basis for cognitive linguistics. These areas of linguistics help in the study of the structural and semantic aspects of language.

Artificial intelligence interacts with cognitive linguistics to explore the capabilities of artificial intelligence systems in language comprehension and use. With the help of artificial intelligence, the processes of automatic analysis, translation and understanding of the language are studied.

Psycholinguistics studies the connections between language and psychology. Research in this area helps to understand the relationship between language and thinking, the processes of language learning and the cognitive foundations of language.

Conclusion

In conclusion, it can be said that cognitive linguistics and cognitive psychology are disciplines that study different aspects of the human mind, with interrelated and complementary areas of research. These disciplines help to understand the complex relationship between language and thinking, the processes of learning and understanding language, and how cognitive processes work. The relationship of cognitive linguistics with other disciplines also indicates the richness and versatility of this science.

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